

The application of IoT in smart homes

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Abstract: The Internet of Things (IoT) has been heralded as the next technology revolution in recent decades since it has made everything inherently linked. Our household items may now be connected to the internet and operated from anywhere on the planet. This is made possible by specialized sensors, actuators, and switches that are connected to network-enabled home appliances like lights, televisions, refrigerators, doors, gates, and air conditioning systems, to mention a few. Connectivity technologies such as 3G/4G/5G, Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, high-speed packet access (HSPA), general packet radio service (GPRS), Long-Term Evolution (LTE), and others are used to connect these sensors, actuators, and switches to the internet. Apps on our smartphones, tablets, laptops, and desktops may then be used to operate these home appliances from anywhere on the planet. A "smart home" or "smart house" is a house with lighting, heating, and technological gadgets that can be controlled remotely by a smartphone or computer. This article explains how Internet of Things (IoT) technology may be used to remotely operate network-capable household appliances. The entire smart home system will be displayed with the smart home's component parts, such as smart gadgets with interoperability capabilities, a smart home gateway or central control box, a smart home network, mobile apps, and online applications for remote access. Additionally, a smart home system's benefits and drawbacks will be discussed.

Keywords: Internet of Things (IoT), IoT sensors, IoT actuators, IoT switches, Smart Home

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Introduction

A smart home is a convenient house setup in which appliances and equipment may be automatically managed remotely using a mobile or other networked device from anywhere with an internet connection. A smart home's devices are linked together over the internet, allowing the user to handle features such as home security, temperature, lighting, and a home theater from afar [1]. A smart house, according to [2] is a sort of home automation system in which a number of Internet of Things (IoT) devices collaborate to provide intelligent control and monitoring functions for homeowners. A Smart Home Gateway connects many smart home devices, provides hardware interfaces for different smart home communication protocols, executes communication protocols, transforms and bridges protocols, and allows user control terminal and cloud server interaction. ITU-T J.1612 tries to describe the architecture of a smart home gateway (SHGW) that fulfills ITU-T J.1611's functional requirements. The proposal includes ideas such as a vir-

tual device model, a dynamic device profile, and other critical software components [2]. With the inclusion of certain critical components, the architecture can alter dynamically. This study review's main goal is to show how Internet of Things (IoT) technology may be utilized to remotely operate household appliances. An overview of the smart home IoT ecosystem is illustrated in figure 1 below.

Fig. 1: An overview of the smart home IoT ecosystem [4]

The overall smart home system

The International Telecommunication Union's (ITU) International Standardization Sector (ITU-T) [3] is in charge of looking into technical, operational, and tariff concerns and making recommendations in order to standardize telecommunications globally. A smart home is a home automation system in which a range of Internet of Things (IoT) devices in the home collaborate to give inhabitants with sophisticated control and monitoring capabilities [3]. The home automation system is made up of smart home devices, a cloud server, a user app, and a smart home gateway, according to ITU-T Rec. J. 1612 (01/2022) 3 [3]. Smart home gadgets include network-enabled appliances, sensors, actuators, and switches, among other things. Because there are so many distinct wireless technologies and protocols used by different devices, they are essentially aggregated by the smart home gateway. These devices link to the physical world in order to gather data and send it to the smart home gateway, which receives and executes the device control instruction. The cloud server is frequently used to store enormous amounts of data such as user information, device information, and service profiles owing to its infinite storage space and high CPU power. Advanced services, such as linkage services that communicate with other eco-systems, are typically implemented on the cloud with a powerful CPU. After that, the decision is transmitted to a smart home gateway, which converts the command into the suitable format and transmits it to the relevant device. Apart from that, cloud-based user management and

authentication, device management (DM), and other sophisticated services are commonly used. The user app, which is a smart terminal such as a smartphone or tablet, usually has a strong processor and a simple UI. Users connect with the smart home system using client programs that run on them, doing tasks like as turning devices on and off, monitoring their status, and establishing time services, among others. Finally, the Smart Home Gateway (SHGW), a critical component of the system, connects various smart home devices, provides hardware interfaces for various smart home communication protocols, runs communication protocols, performs protocol conversion and bridging, realizes device discovery and authentication access, and realizes interaction between the user control terminal and the cloud server, such as requesting the device and service profile from the cloud server.

Fig. 2: The overall smart home system [3]

Smart Home Components

The resources needed to build a smart home, according to the authors in [5], include smart devices with interoperability capabilities, a smart home gateway or central control box, a smart home network, mobile apps, and web applications for remote access. The many networked household equipment that may be found in a smart home are depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Connected devices in a smart home [5]

Interoperability Capabilities

In fact, there has been a substantial development in the smart home sector during the past few years. Modern smart home technologies have the ability to boost consumer comfort and convenience, provide home security, and aid in energy conservation. Adopting the benefits provided by smart home technology is hampered by technological fragmentation. Technological fragmentation, which occurs when each item in a system must be operated independently, can have a detrimental impact on the user experience and provide an adoption hurdle. Interoperability is crucial for removing the obstacle. Interoperability refers to a system, application, device, or service's capacity to function reliably in conjunction with one another in the context of a smart home. A smart home's many equipment may interact with one another and cooperate thanks to interoperability. By doing so, complexity is reduced to a minimum and user misunderstanding may be prevented. For this reason, interoperability in smart homes is crucial.

Smart Home Gateway or Central Control Box

The industry is expanding, and even conservative predictions indicate that in the next years, there will be a noticeable rise in the number of homes managed by SmartHome technology. Each SmartHome system's central control unit serves as a gateway, connecting all of the system's parts and allowing access from the outside. It also determines how intelligent the system is. Many manufacturers now provide basic parts with capabilities like heating control, security monitoring, or window closure before it starts to rain. The Internet of Things (IoT) contains an increasing number of gadgets, some of which are extremely basic, yet they can interact with one another and work in tandem. The SmartHome Gateway proposed in [6] uses PnP to wirelessly link all components. It serves as the brain of the networked home, and applications may quickly and intuitively manage it both within and beyond the walls of the house. The system is guarded against unauthorised access by using the most up-to-date coding and an optional connection over GSM/UMTS with a SIM card. Future functioning of the system is ensured by the Z-Wave and Q-Wave protocols, which are supported along with an embedded WLAN module. These standards guarantee compatibility with nearly all known SmartHome components.

Fig. 4: Smart home gateway [6]

Smart Home Network

A house that employs internet-connected appliances to provide remote monitoring and control of systems and appliances, such as lighting and heating, is referred to as a smart home. According to [8], a "smart house network" is a handy configuration of a home in which equipment and appliances may be remotely controlled automatically from any location with an internet connection using a mobile or other networked device. An internet-connected network connects the devices in a smart home, enabling users to remotely control features like temperature, lighting, home theater, and security access [9]. With the use of a smartphone or tablet and an internet connection, a smart home gives its owners remote access to control lights, appliances, thermostats, and other equipment. Wireless or hardwired

technologies can be used to build up smart houses. Homeowners may save money and enjoy convenience thanks to smart home technologies. Makers and consumers of smart home technologies are still hampered by security concerns and vulnerabilities [8].

Fig. 5: Smart home network [9]

Mobile Apps and Web Applications for Remote Access

Remote access refers to the capability for an authorized user to connect to a computer or network across a network from a distance. Users who are physically far away from the systems they require can connect via remote access. The authors [10] proposed an Internet of Things (IoT) based Smart Home Design using Power and Security Management that aims to have multiple advantages, including lowering home electricity bills, keeping users informed about their home security with the option of controlling the switching of the devices by using their voice or simple toggle touch on their smartphone. A smart home's features may be controlled and tracked via an android app. The software must be linked to the internet through mobile data or Wi-Fi because it is based on open source Android development. The user has the option to look for Wi-Fi devices in the app's welcome screen if there is no mobile data available to connect to the internet. The user also has the choice to examine the status of the connected devices, access the Touch Mode, access the Voice Mode, and modify the app's settings. The user may use the tap-to-toggle technique to control how the switches are toggled in the Touch Mode as illustrated in figure 7. Simply touching on the toggle for the current state will alter the device's current status. This app's most user-friendly feature allows users to change a device's status using one of the voice commands that are offered as depicted in figure 8. The functionality employs the built-in speech recognition capability of the Google API, which automatically detects the available commands and provides the appropriate result. The user has the option to browse through the list and play the voice command. The energy management mode in the view status mode allows the user to keep an eye on the real-time location of their

gadgets. It shows the device's current condition and the amount of energy it was using. If the device has been on for a long time, it provides an alert regarding its consumption time so the user can keep track.

Fig. 6: Android App Home Screen [10]

Fig. 7: Android App Touch Mode [10]

Fig. 8: Android App Voice Mode [10]

Fig. 9: Android App View Status Tab [10]

The Advantages of Smart Homes

One of the most lauded advantages of home automation is its ability to provide owners piece of mind by enabling them to monitor their properties from a distance and fending against threats like an unlocked front door. The

author [6] expanded on certain advantages of smart homes, claiming that the elderly may also profit from domotics since they provide monitoring that enables the elderly to remain at home comfortably and safely instead of having to enter a nursing home or requiring 24-hour home care. Users have the option of programming their garage door to open, lights to turn on, fireplace to light, and preferred music to play when they arrive. Consumers can increase efficiency with the use of home automation. A smart home system may learn from behavior and ensure that the house is cooled down by the time owners get home from work instead of turning on the air conditioning throughout the day. Appliances follow the same rules. The grass will only be watered when necessary and with the precise amount of water required with a smart irrigation system. Home automation makes it possible to use energy, water, and other resources more effectively, which helps consumers save both money and natural resources.

The Disadvantages of Smart Homes

Because of their technological nature, home automation systems have had a difficult time entering the public. The apparent complexity of smart homes is a disadvantage; some individuals struggle with technology or give up on it at the first hurdle. In order to make smart homes fun and useful for users of all sorts and technical levels, manufacturers and partnerships are lowering complexity and improving the user experience. Devices must use the same protocol, or at the very least complimentary ones, and be compatible with one another regardless of manufacturer for home automation systems to be truly successful. There is currently no industry standard for home automation because it is a relatively young industry. In contrast, standard alliances are working with manufacturers and protocols to guarantee compatibility and a seamless user experience. Smart home security is a significant problem as well. According to a 2016 NTT Data Corp. research, 80% of American consumers are worried about the security of the data from their smart homes [6]. Hackers who get access to a smart device may be able to disable the lights, alarms, and doors, rendering a house vulnerable to intrusion. Additionally, hackers may get access to the homeowner's network, which might result in harsher assaults or data theft. Using poorly protected cameras, DVRs, and routers as entry points, the Mirai IoT botnet was able to knock down portions of the internet in October 2016 through a series of distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) assaults [6]. Many smart home critics also worry about data privacy in addition to home security. According to the NTT Data survey, 73% of customers are worried about the privacy of the information supplied by their smart home gadgets. Manufacturers of smart home platforms and devices may gather consumer data to better customize their goods or provide consumers with new and enhanced services, but building trust and being transparent are essential if they hope to attract new clients.

Conclusions

A "smart home" or "smart house" is a house with technological features that can be operated remotely from a smartphone or computer, including lighting, heating, and other systems. This article was written to demonstrate how Internet of Things (IoT) technology may be used to remotely operate network-capable home appliances. Along with the core elements of a smart home, such as interoperable smart gadgets, a smart home gateway or central control box, a smart home network, mobile apps, and online applications for remote access, the entire smart home system was displayed. A smart home's advantages and disadvantages were also discussed.

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